

Three-dimensional finite-element analysis of transverse stresses in sandwich plates.

A. ATE, S. AIVAZZADEH, G. VERCHERY

*Université de Bourgogne, Institut Supérieur de l'Automobile et des Transports, Laboratoire de Recherche en Mécanique et Acoustique
49 Rue Mademoiselle Bourgeois, B.P. 31, 58027 Nevers cedex, France
E-Mail: Alain-Martial.Ate_isat@u-bourgogne.fr*

ABSTRACT In this paper, we present an interface finite-element designed for three-dimensional stress analysis in multilayers structures. The element is an eight-node brick element based on the Hellinger-Reissner mixed variational principle. Degrees of freedom at each node include three transverse stress components of the stress tensor, and three translation displacement components. This definition leads to stress equilibrium and displacement continuity through the interface. Results of a numerical example involving a sandwich plate show the effectiveness of the element model.

KEYWORDS : Heterogeneous materials, Sandwich plates, Interface finite-element, Interface continuity, Mixed variational principle, Stress analysis, Displacement.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the classical displacements based finite-element account for displacement continuity through the element boundaries. However in finite-element analyses using such an approach, the main problem is the respect of the stress equilibrium in the element boundaries, though high order polynomial approximations are used for the element formulation. This is particularly true across the interface of dissimilar materials where stress singularities usually occur. The interface here indicates the common boundary area of two dissimilar materials, as for sandwich structures or adhesively bonded joints.

On the other hand it should be noticed the importance of the interface stresses in understanding the behaviour of heterogeneous structures in failure. For instance, interlaminar stresses have implications on the initiation of delamination in composite laminates (Pagano [1989]). For an accurate evaluation of interface stresses, it is necessary to satisfy, as far as possible, the continuity of the displacement and stress vectors through the interface boundaries.

In this paper we present a three dimensional mixed finite-element which fulfils the interface continuity requirements. This element is intended to compute transverse stress components through a planar interface. Based on Reissner's mixed functional, the element is an eight-node brick with three transverse stress and three displacement components as degree of freedom at each element node corner, whereas the extra stress components are located inside the element,

and then eliminated from the element level by condensation. In what follows, we give the element development process and treat the problem of a sandwich plate under a uniform load in its upper plane.

ELEMENT FORMULATION

We consider here an interface of two dissimilar materials as shown in Fig. 1. In co-ordinates with the x_1, x_2 plane parallel to the interface, continuity conditions through a perfectly coherent interface are:

$$\begin{cases} T1 + T2 = 0 \\ U1 = U2 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \sigma_{3i}^1 = \sigma_{3i}^2 \\ u_i^1 = u_i^2 \end{cases} \quad i = 1,2,3 \quad (1)$$

T_i , σ^i , and U_i are respectively the stress vector, the stress tensor, and the displacement vector at the point P belonging to the i th material ; $N1$ denotes a unit outward vector normal to the interface at the point P.

Fig. 1 : Stress equilibrium at a point P of an interface.

The transverse stress components σ_{i3} , $i = 1,2,3$ and displacements u_i will be called interface variables. Our aim is to develop a mixed brick element which fulfils the interface continuity conditions expressed in Eqn 1. Therefore the element developed includes as degrees of freedom at each node the interface variables defined above. Fig.2 gives the

geometry and the definition of the element degrees of freedom. Such an element can be used in finite-element analysis to model a ply in laminate composites or a core in a sandwich.

Fig 2: Three-dimensional mixed interface-element.

The starting point in the elementary matrix calculation is the Hellinger-Reissner's mixed functional [1950]. In the case of homogeneous boundary conditions and zero body forces, this functional can be written as :

$$V(\sigma_{ij}, \mathbf{u}_i) = \int_V \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} S_{ijkl} \sigma_{lk} + \sigma_{ij} u_{i,j} \right\} dv \quad (2)$$

Where S_{ijkl} are the material compliance coefficients. In order to avoid the excessive continuity of the stress tensor components, and to reduce the number of degrees of freedom when developing interface mixed finite-elements, Aivazzadeh and Verchery [1984] have proposed a method referred to as 'relocalization process'. The general principle of the method is to affect to the element principle nodes the interface variables, whereas the extra stress components are affected to internal nodes, and then eliminated from the element level by condensation. Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b summarise the process. The internal nodes are homothetic to corner nodes. The variables affected to corner nodes use the same interpolation as for an eight-node brick displacement based finite-element, whereas the extra stress components affected to internal nodes use an equivalent approximation. The different approximations of the element are written in the equations below. These approximations are expressed in intrinsic co-ordinates. The coefficients r_i , s_i and t_i which appear in Eqn. 6 are equal to the ratio of the above-mentioned homothety

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{3i} = \sum_{k=1}^8 N_k(r, s, t) \sigma_{3i}^k \\ \mathbf{u}_i = \sum_{k=1}^8 N_k(r, s, t) \mathbf{u}_i^k \end{cases} \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (3)$$

$$N_i(r, s, t) = \frac{1}{8} (1 + r_i r) (1 + s_i s) (1 + t_i t) \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{\alpha\beta} = \sum_{j=9}^{16} N_j(r, s, t) \sigma_{\alpha\beta}^j \\ \alpha, \beta = 1, 2 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$N_j(r,s,t) = \frac{1}{8} \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_j}\right) \left(1 + \frac{s}{s_j}\right) \left(1 + \frac{t}{t_j}\right) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3a : Derivative element

Static condensation

Fig.3b : Double interface mixed finite-element.

The discrete ‘compliance-stiffness’ matrix equivalent of Eqn 2 is of the form :

$$K_e = \begin{bmatrix} \int_{\Omega_e} N_{\sigma}^T S N_{\sigma} dv & \int_{\Omega_e} N_{\sigma}^T B dv \\ \int_{\Omega_e} B^T N_{\sigma} dv & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{\sigma\sigma} & K_{\sigma u} \\ K_{\sigma u}^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

B denotes the classical strain matrix of a displacement brick element, and N_{σ} the stress interpolation matrix. The matrix expressed in Eqn. 7 is the matrix of the derivative element defined in Fig. 3a, it is a square matrix of 72 degrees of freedom. The internal stress component degrees of freedom which contribute to increasing the bandwidth of the assembled

matrix are eliminated by a static condensation in the element level. This condensation leads to a 48 degrees of freedom square matrix. Contrary to the full matrix, the sub-matrix extract from the condensed matrix, and relative to the displacement degrees of freedom is not null. Tests for elementary convergence of the element have been performed with success, these are tests for completeness and compatibility criteria. In the following section, an example problem concerning the stress calculation in a sandwich plate is treated. Results obtained using the element developed are compared with available elasticity and other finite element models.

NUMERICALS RESULTS

We consider here a sandwich plate simply supported on all edges, and loaded by a unit uniform force in its upper surface. The material of the facing is orthotropic whereas the core is transversely orthotropic. The geometry and material data are given in the figure below.

Fig 4 : Geometry and material data of the sandwich plate.

In the finite-element analysis, the quarter of the plate is modelled by 10 elements along the length, and 8 by 8 elements through the cross section. In this analysis, only the interfacial stress components σ_{3i} and the displacements are computed. The numerical results obtained using our interface finite-element are compared with the elasticity solution thanks to Pagano [1970]. Pagano's solution uses a three-dimensional theoretical approach wherein the displacement components and the stress tensor components are directly computed. Fig. 5 shows the distribution of the shear stress σ_{31} through the thickness at different locations. The finite-element results are in good agreement with the theory. Similar conclusion can be made for the others interfacial stresses σ_{32} and σ_{33} , Fig. 6 for instance shows the distribution of the normal stress σ_{33} through the thickness at the middle of the sandwich plate.

Comparisons also include results using others finite-element models for two values of the ratio a/h . The DSQ (Discrete Shear Quadrilateral) element is a four-node quadrilateral based on the theory of Mindlin-Reissner for the thick plates. This element is due to Batoz [1992]. The ANSYS-solid solution is obtained with the displacement eight-nodes brick element. The centre-point deflexion is shown in Tables 1 and 2, together with the shear stresses σ_{31} and σ_{32} . These quantities are rendered dimensionless by multiplying u_3 by $(10E_{22}h^3)/(qa^4)$; σ_{31} and σ_{32}

by $(10^5 h)/(E_{22} a)$. The results of the presented element are compared favourably with these two models. However the displacement brick element yields less accuracy.

Fig. 5 : Shear stress σ_{31} distribution through the thickness.

Fig. 6 : Normal stress σ_{33} distribution through the thickness.

Table. 1 Comparison of different computation methods for the plate ratio $a/h=5$.

a/h = 5		P1(x1=a/2,x2=b/2,x3=h/2)	P2(x1=a/4,x2=b/4,x3=t)	
t/h	computation method	u_3	σ_{31}	σ_{32}
0.10	Pagano	2.473	2.493	1.904
	Interfacial FE	2.449	2.444	1.901
	ANSYS-solid	2.184	4.163	0.251
	DSQ	2.559	2.425	1.880
0.01	Pagano	9.328	2.949	0.893
	Interfacial FE	9.340	2.253	1.072
	ANSYS-solid	8.736	4.468	1.560
	DSQ	9.632	2.300	0.908

Table. 2 Comparison of different computation methods for the plate ratio $a/h=10$.

a/h = 10		Point P1	Point P2	
t/h	Computation method	u_3	σ_{31}	σ_{32}
0.10	Pagano	1.647	3.195	1.420
	Interfacial FE	1.631	3.223	1.422
	ANSYS-solid	1.512	2.990	1.308
	DSQ	1.694	3.282	1.384
0.01	Pagano	8.474	2.314	0.875
	Interfacial FE	8.393	2.371	1.009
	ANSYS-solidsoli	8.022	2.624	1.456
	DSQ	8.561	2.521	0.838

CONCLUSION

A model of interface brick element based on Hellinger-Reissner mixed variational principle has been presented in this paper. This element fulfils the interface continuity requirements. Numerical results of a test involving a sandwich plate have shown good agreement between the element model and the Pagano theoretical solution. Comparisons have also been made favourably with other finite-element models. In fact the interface mixed finite-element presented in this paper must be placed within the framework of the research on interfacial finite-elements initiated by Verchery and Aivazzadeh.[1984]. Research is in progress to apply the element model to failure analyses.

REFERENCES

- 1 Até, A.M., "Eléments finis mixtes tridimensionnels pour le calcul des champs de contraintes dans les structures hétérogènes", *Thèse de Doctorat de l'Université de Bourgogne, spécialité Mécanique*, 1998.
2. Até, A.M., Aivazzadeh, S., Verchery, G, "Three-dimensional mixed finite-element analysis for heterogeneous structures with applications to adhesively bonded joints and sandwich plates", *Computer methods in composite materials VI*, Wit Press, 1998, pp. 373-382.
- 3 Aivazzadeh, S., "Finite elements for the analysis of interface,with application to laminates structures", *Proceedings of the fourth French Conference on Composites*, ed., Pluralis, Paris, 1984, pp 376-392.
- 4 Penado, F.E and Dropeck, R.K., "Numerical Design and Analysis", *Engineered Materials Handbook Vol 3*, ASM, pp 477-500.
- 5 Reissner, E., "On variational Theorem in Elasticity", *Journal of Mathematics and Physics*, Vol.29, Jan 1950, pp 90-95.
- 6 Vannucci, P., Aivazzadeh, S., Verchery, "G,A comparative analysis of some theories and finite-elements for sandwich plates and shells", *Proceedings of the Euromech 360 colloquium held in Saint-Etienne, France, 13-15 May 1997* Kluwer Academic Publishers pp 45-52.
- 7 Pagano, N.J, Soni, S.R., "Models for studying free-edge effects", *Composites Materials Series : Volume 5*, Series Editor : R.B. Pipes Elsevier pp 2-68.